

A holistic assessment of farmers' intention to adopt agroecological practices – The case of Swiss grassland

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ABSTRACT

Agroecology provides a holistic approach to sustainable agriculture. Although the concept is gaining increasing interest, there is a lack of knowledge regarding farmers' intentions to adopt agroecological practices, and existing studies do not account for its holistic approach. We analyze farmers' intentions to adopt agroecological practices across four key elements of agroecology: diversity, synergy, efficiency, and recycling. We assess a wide range of potential drivers, including farm and farmer characteristics, natural conditions, expected opportunity costs, and behavioral factors. Our focus is on grassland farming in the Swiss mountain region, a production system with high agroecological potential. We combine survey data collected between April and May 2024 from 495 farmers, with agricultural census data and weather data. Our analysis shows that farmers' intentions to adopt agroecology are highest for practices related to recycling, followed by practices that increase synergies, farm diversity, and efficiency. Further, we find that social norms (i.e., injunctive norms, descriptive norms, and signaling motives) are key drivers for scaling up agroecology across all elements. Economic factors primarily relate to the adoption of elements of agroecology especially where higher investments (i.e., solar panels and biogas) are required. The results suggest that measures focusing on farmers' social norms, such as nudges or information campaigns, could support scaling up agroecology. Further, our results highlight the multifaceted nature of agroecology, particularly its interconnected elements and the importance of behavioral factors for adoption intentions. We conclude that a one-size-fits-all approach to the different elements of agroecology is unlikely to be efficient in scaling up agroecology.

1. Introduction

Agriculture is an important contributor to major environmental and societal challenges worldwide (Springmann et al., 2018). To tackle these challenges, there is a need for a transformation toward more sustainable practices while maintaining current production levels (Dhankher and Foyer, 2018; Pratap et al., 2024). Agroecology offers a promising approach to the sustainable transformation of agriculture (Gliessman, 2018; Nicholls and Altieri, 2018). It is a transdisciplinary approach that applies ecological concepts and principles to agri-food systems on different scales (FAO, 2018; Bezner Kerr et al., 2021). Key elements of agroecology are (1) increasing farm diversity, (2) building synergies between different production branches of farms, (3) improving efficiency, and (4) increasing renewable energy production and biomass recycling. The performance of ecological systems therefore emerges from multiple practices and interrelates across the different elements of

agroecology. Various policy goals and initiatives to increase agroecological farming exist at a regional and national level, such as the European Green Deal or the Agroecology Switzerland resource project.¹ However, evidence of the factors influencing farmers' intentions to adopt agroecology is limited and restricted to single elements of agroecology, thereby failing to reflect the holistic, system-oriented approach of the concept (Ewert et al., 2023).

This study aims to investigate and compare farmers' intentions to adopt agroecological practices across four key elements—diversity, synergy, efficiency, and recycling—and to examine the underlying drivers influencing the adoption of each element. We consider potential drivers, such as farm and farmer characteristics, weather conditions, and behavioral factors, which have been shown to be of central importance in the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices (e.g., Dessart et al., 2019; Finger et al., 2024). Our study focuses on grassland farming in the Swiss mountain region because agroecology's holistic approach is

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¹ <https://www.agroecology.science/en/projekte/agraroekologie-schweiz.html>

particularly relevant for grassland ecosystems, which are under pressure from climate change, land use change, and intensive agricultural practices (Bengtsson et al., 2019; Weber et al., 2024). To conduct this analysis, we combine survey data from 495 grassland farms in the Swiss mountain region, selected to be structurally representative of the regional farming population, with farm structural data from the Swiss Agricultural Information System and weather data from MeteoSwiss.

The existing literature highlights the great variety of agroecological practices that can be found in grassland farms (Peeters and Wezel, 2017). However, although there are various studies on the adoption and implementation of agri-environmental schemes (Lastra-Bravo et al., 2015; Mack et al., 2019; Pavlis et al., 2016; Uthes and Matzdorf, 2013), information on farmers' intentions to adopt agroecological practices is limited. Moreover, the existing literature on agroecology acknowledges the interlinkages among the different agroecological elements that target different aspects of agricultural production (Wezel et al., 2020; Zhu et al., 2024). Nevertheless, studies assessing farmers' adoption intentions across different elements are lacking. This highlights the need to understand how farmers design their agroecological farming systems and make management decisions. Multiple aspects, including the characteristics of farms and farmers and economic and institutional factors, play a crucial role in farmers' decision-making processes. Recent literature further shows that behavioral factors are especially relevant in the adoption of sustainable farming practices (Crudeli et al., 2022; Dessart et al., 2019; Finger et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2018; Prokopy et al., 2008). Hence, gaining insights into these factors is crucial to identifying the barriers that may prevent the adoption and scaling up of agroecology.

We contribute to the literature with the first holistic analysis of agroecological practices. We analyze practices related to the four key elements of agroecology that guide the transition to sustainable farming systems: diversity, synergy, efficiency, and recycling (FAO, 2018; Gliessman, 2018). First, we descriptively assess and compare farmers' intentions to adopt agroecological practices related to these four elements. Second, we use regression analysis to examine the drivers of farmers' intentions to adopt these practices.

Our findings show that farmers' intentions to adopt practices vary among the different elements of agroecology. Specifically, we observe the highest level of intention to increase practices related to recycling, followed by practices related to synergies and diversity. However, farmers also intend to decrease practices related to the element of efficiency. Our analysis reveals that the drivers of adoption vary across the different elements of agroecology, although certain patterns can be observed. In particular, social norms play a central role in the adoption of agroecological practices across all elements. Based on our results, we discuss policy implications for scaling up agroecology.

The remainder of the article is structured as follows. We begin by providing background information on agroecology in grassland farming, summarize relevant agroecological practices, and present our theoretical framework. We then describe the data used in the analysis, followed by the descriptive statistics and results of our empirical analysis. We conclude with a discussion of the findings and their implications for research and policy.

2. Background and conceptual framework

2.1. Agroecology and its relevance in grassland farming

In this paper, we define agroecology based on the United Nations report as a transdisciplinary approach that applies ecological concepts and principles to agri-food systems on various scales (Bezner Kerr et al., 2022; HLPE, 2019). We use the '10 Elements of Agroecology' framework developed by the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO, 2018),² which provides guidance on the transition to

sustainable farming and food systems (Gliessman, 2018). Following the FAO's framing, agroecology is understood as a holistic and integrated approach that simultaneously addresses the ecological, economic, and social dimensions of the food system. The 10 elements of agroecology are interlinked and interdependent. Therefore, a holistic approach is necessary to capture the complexity and interconnectedness of agroecological practice adoption. In this analysis, we focus on sustainable farming systems and four related agroecological elements: diversity, synergy, efficiency, and recycling. Transitioning toward agroecology may require more than changing only individual practices; it can involve rethinking the farm's entire business model, with greater diversification, enhanced recycling, and stronger links to alternative markets (Sanchez-Mata et al., 2025). The specific changes, however, will likely vary depending on the type of farm and its production system. This further motivates our focus on grassland farms, where these elements are key on the farm level. According to FAO's (2018) description of these elements, *diversity* encompasses species variety and ecological interactions within farming systems. It can support farm productivity, resilience, nutrition, and sustainability while reducing climatic and genetic risks. *Synergy* refers to the beneficial interactions between different farming components, such as soil, trees, livestock, and water. Synergy between these systems can improve resource use, reduce costs, and enhance system health and resilience. *Efficiency* captures the wise use of resources by managing diversity and synergies. Increasing efficiency can reduce inputs, costs, and environmental harm, boosting farmers' independence and resilience. The element of recycling in agroecology reflects the reuse of nutrients, water, and biomass within farming systems. It aims at cutting waste and input, improving effectiveness, and strengthening long-term sustainability and self-reliance.

Grassland systems are of great importance within agroecology due to their potential to support biodiversity, improve soil fertility, and provide feed for livestock (Weber et al., 2024). The element of diversity is highly relevant in grassland farming (Dumont et al., 2022). Increasing the diversity of belowground organisms, plants, insects, and animals in grassland farming systems can enhance resilience by improving adaptation to extreme weather events (Bardgett and van der Putten, 2014; Isbell et al., 2015). Increasing sward diversity can strengthen soil carbon accumulation, soil health, and livestock productivity while promoting ecosystem stability (Hofmann and Isselstein, 2005; Yang et al., 2019). Different livestock species on grassland farms can enhance pasture use (Dumont et al., 2022; Martin et al., 2020). Diversifying farm income through different production branches and sales (e.g., direct sales or agro-tourism) can make farms more independent of external inputs and more resilient (Altieri and Nicholls, 2017). Integrating agritourism activities, such as farm tours, workshops, and equipment leasing, creates additional revenue streams and promotes community involvement (Schilling et al., 2012).

The element of synergies in grassland farming systems emerges through the interconnectedness of various ecosystem services and the integration of livestock management within sustainable forage production (e.g., alpine pastures) (Qian et al., 2021). Well-managed grazing demonstrates synergies between livestock and the ecosystem through nutrient cycling and enhanced soil fertility (Li et al., 2020). In addition, integrating trees and hedges alongside pastures can provide shade and shelter for livestock while improving carbon sequestration and biodiversity (Kay et al., 2019). Feeding milk to young animals facilitates synergistic interactions within agroecological systems by using on-farm resources and reducing dependence on external feed sources, thereby increasing sustainability and resilience in livestock production (FAO, 2018).

In grassland farming, efficiency is manifested through practices that optimize resource utilization while minimizing the use of external inputs. For instance, feeding animals with locally available feedstuff reduces dependence on purchased feed (Hayat et al., 2024), lowers production costs, and increases reliance on self-produced forage (Leiber et al., 2025; Soteriades et al., 2020). Furthermore, the application of

² <https://www.fao.org/agroecology/overview/overview10elements/en/>

preventive health strategies increases efficiency by improving animal welfare and decreasing reliance on unplanned veterinary services (Soussana et al., 2020). The element of recycling includes the use of solar energy on farms, which can reduce reliance on fossil fuels and energy costs and contribute to a more sustainable production system. Additionally, converting agricultural residues and livestock manure into compost can enhance soil fertility and structure while reducing the need for synthetic fertilizers.

2.2. Conceptual model for explaining farmers' adoption of agroecological farming practices

Effective agroecological transitions entails for farms to integrate natural, physical, socio-economic and human resources into its operations. Therefore, our first step is the construction of a conceptual model (Sanchez-Mata et al., 2025). Our first step is the construction of a conceptual model. We summarize findings from the literature on the characteristics of farms and farmers that may relate to the adoption of sustainable agricultural practices. Next, we consider external factors, such as weather conditions, followed by an analysis of the behavioral factors that shape farmers' adoption intentions. Fig. 1 provides an overview of our conceptual model.

Farmers' characteristics, including gender, may influence the adoption of agroecological practices. For example, a German study showed that female-led farms are more likely to participate in animal welfare programs (Heise and Theuvsen, 2016). However, findings on how gender influences the adoption of sustainable farming practices in Europe are mixed (Burton et al., 2003; Mzoughi, 2011). Age and education can be similarly influential factors (Siebert et al., 2010). Better education can also support farmers in adopting sustainable practices (Chatzimichael et al., 2014; Mzoughi, 2011). However, adoption does not always increase with better education. Some studies have reported that adoption rates may even decrease or remain stable beyond a certain level of education (Burton et al., 2003; Chatzimichael et al., 2014; Läßle and Kelley, 2015). In addition, farm succession is critical to strategic farm decision-making. For example, farmers are more likely to invest when they know that they have a successor (Daniele, 2024).

Farm characteristics are also important in the adoption of agroecological practices. However, the impact of farm size on the adoption of sustainable farming practices remains a topic of debate (Burton et al.,

2003; Chatzimichael et al., 2014; Läßle, 2010; Läßle and Rensburg, 2011), with larger farms often assumed to have greater financial resources, supporting the adoption of sustainable technologies. Moreover, a farm's current level of agroecological performance may affect its intention to adopt further agroecological practices. For example, those with already high levels of agroecological practices may be less inclined to adopt further practices, although positive experiences with the current level of agroecology may encourage further adoption, while negative experiences may discourage it (Sattler et al., 2010; Schukat et al., 2020; Siebert et al., 2010; Winkel et al., 2022). Weather conditions, such as water availability and climate, can influence farms' suitability for certain sustainable practices (Njuki et al., 2018).

Furthermore, behavioral factors, including cognitive, social, and dispositional factors, may play an important role in the adoption of agroecological practices (Castro Campos, 2022; Dessart et al., 2019). Research has shown that cognitive factors, such as perceived costs, knowledge of the practices, financial risk assessments, and perceived control (i.e., the belief that one can control one's actions), influence the adoption of sustainable practices among farmers (Kallas et al., 2010; Läßle and Rensburg, 2011; Mante and Gerowitz, 2009; Niens and Marggraf, 2010; Trujillo-Barrera et al., 2016). Although the potential for increased profitability may encourage the transition toward sustainable farming systems, the perception of higher financial risks can act as barriers (Dessart et al., 2019; Trujillo-Barrera et al., 2016). Perceived support is another factor that influences farmers' intention to adopt sustainable practices (Ridwansyah et al., 2024), while a lack of available resources (i.e., infrastructure, technical resources) can hinder the adoption intention (Valdivia et al., 2012).

Social factors also play a key role in shaping farmer behavior. Dessart et al. (2019) described these as a process that captures the influence of others on individual decision-making, encompassing perceptions of social approval, peer behavior, and reputation-related motives. Although the model does not adhere to a single theoretical model, such as the Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1991), the typologies integrate concepts that are linked by capturing multiple dimensions of social influence. Dessart et al. (2019) distinguished between three types of norms: (1) injunctive norms (i.e., what I believe that key actors such as consultants, society, environmentalists, peers, and scientists think I should do), (2) descriptive norms (i.e., what my peers are doing), and (3) signaling motives (i.e., what can improve my image). Injunctive norms

Fig. 1. Overview of factors influencing farmers' intention to adopt agroecological practices.

influence decisions through the perception of social approval. In line with this perspective, our study incorporates all three types of social influence to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how social dynamics influence decision-making. For example, farmers may adopt practices that are perceived to be socially valued, especially if they are influenced by key actors, as demonstrated by studies emphasizing the role of social approval in behavioral adoption (Borges et al., 2014; Lienhoop and Brouwer, 2015; Schreiner and Hess, 2017; Sereke et al., 2016; Siebert et al., 2010; Van Soest et al., 2015).

Descriptive norms can increase the adoption of sustainable farming practices (e.g., organic farming) (Läpple and Kelley, 2015). This peer influence extends to various areas, such as livestock vaccinations (Sok et al., 2016) and reflects individuals' tendency to conform to the majority (Asch, 1956). Additionally, Niens and Marggraf (2010) showed that farmers may adopt sustainable practices to improve the image of their farms. Measures focusing on farmers' social norms, such as nudges or information campaigns, could positively influence the adoption of sustainable farming practices (Buchholz and Musshoff, 2021; Kuhfuss et al., 2016; El Benni et al., 2026). Dispositional factors refer to stable individual traits, including farmers' moral and environmental concerns, resistance to change, and risk tolerance. They shape farmers' behavioral intentions and capacity for change (Bakker et al., 2021; Dessart et al., 2019). Farmers who demonstrate a strong sense of environmental or moral concern are more inclined to adopt sustainable practices, even in the absence of clear economic incentives (Burton et al., 2003; Läpple, 2010). Although based on the classification of Dessart et al.'s (2019) our framework is closely aligned with the work of Amare and Darr (2020). In their review, the authors grouped the factors of agroforestry innovation adoption into the innovation itself (e.g., cost-effectiveness, compatibility, and economic and non-monetary benefits), the household context (e.g., household livelihood, resources, social relations, and the perceptions of sharing adoption decisions), and the system-level factors (e.g., environmental and institutional circumstances) (Amare and Darr, 2020). Although our classification and terminology differ slightly, the factors identified are largely comparable. The main difference is that system-level factors are less emphasized in our study, as they are strongly associated with farmers' actual adoption behavior, whereas our study primarily measures farmers' adoption intentions.

Given this premise, we assume that a utility-maximizing farmer would consider these factors as follows (e.g., Möhring and Finger, 2022:

$$(1) \text{Max}_A E \left[U \left(\pi_{ie} \left(A_{ie}, X_{ie}, W_{ie}, \text{Adj}_{ie}, \epsilon_{ie}^A \right), BF_{ie} \right) \right],$$

where U represents the von-Neumann–Morgenstern utility function of the farmer i , and practices linked to different agroecology elements are represented by $e \in \{\text{diversity, synergies, efficiency, and recycling}\}$. $\pi_{ie} \left(A_{ie}, X_{ie}, W_{ie}, \text{Adj}_{ie}, \epsilon_{ie}^A \right)$ is the profit function of farmer i , for which A_{ie} denotes the farmer's adoption intention of agroecological practices, X_{ie} represents farm and farmer characteristics, such as farm type, size, the current agroecological performance of the farm, and management related factors, W_{ie} represents natural conditions, Adj_{ie} denotes the potential adjustment costs associated with switching to the new system, and ϵ_{ie}^A represents uncertainty in production and unobservable factors influencing farmers' decision-making. BF_{ie} denotes behavioral factors such as cognitive, social, and dispositional factors.

Utility maximization in this context refers to the assumption that farmers aim to make decisions that they expect will best improve their overall utility from all factors considered here, including economic returns (captured by the profit function π_{ie} but also consideration for behavioral factors such as cognitive, social, and dispositional factors BF_{ie}). This reflects the multi-attribute consideration where farmers weigh the trade-off between profitability, risk, adjustment costs, and personal or social motivations. Expected utility allows for the incorporation of both risks and expectations, which are deemed important for

farmers' decisions.

For a utility-maximizing farmer to adopt (additional) agroecological practices, the following condition must therefore be satisfied:

$$(2) E \left[U \left(\pi_{ie} \left(A_{ie}^{A=1}, X_{ie}, W_{ie}, \text{Adj}_{ie}, \epsilon_{ie}^{A=1} \right), BF_{ie} \right) \right] \\ \geq E \left[U \left(\pi_{ie} \left(A_{ie}^{A=0}, X_{ie}, W_{ie}, \epsilon_{ie}^{A=0} \right), BF_{ie} \right) \right]$$

Based on the literature discussed above, we derive the following hypotheses concerning the factors influencing a farmer's intention to adopt practices (Table 1). These hypotheses guide the empirical analysis that follows.

3. Methods

3.1. Databases and sample

For our empirical analyses, we combined survey data with data from the Swiss agricultural national census database AGIS (FOAG, 2020) and weather data from MeteoSwiss. We conducted a farmer survey between April and May 2024 in the German- and French-speaking parts of Switzerland. For this purpose, we randomly selected 2001 specialized grassland farms located in the Swiss mountain region from the AGIS.³ The sample included farms operating under the legal forms of natural and simple persons and collective farms. Farm types encompassed year-round operations, joint ventures, and farming communities. The survey was available in French and German, translated by a professional translation service, and subsequently reviewed by a native speaker to ensure accuracy.

A prior power analysis was conducted using G*Power (Version 3.1.9.7; Faul et al., 2007) to assess the adequacy of the sample from two complementary perspectives. First, to ensure sufficient power to represent the population of approximately 14,000 grassland farms in the Swiss mountain region, we assumed a medium effect size ($w = 0.3$). With a significance level of alpha of 0.05 (two-tailed) and a desired statistical power of 0.8, our analysis indicated a required minimum sample size of approximately 232 farms. Second, considering the planned multivariate analysis including 26 predictors, a separate a priori power analysis assuming a medium effect size ($f^2 = 0.15$) indicated that at least 175 responses were required to achieve a statistical power of 0.8 at an alpha of 0.05. In both cases, the invited sample of 2001 farms is sufficient even under a conservative expected response rate of approximately 20%, consistent with the response rates reported in previous studies of farmer adoption in Switzerland (e.g., Möhring and Finger, 2022).

Stratification of language regions (only French and German) and farming zones (i.e., mountain farming zones 1–4; see Table 2 & Appendix I & J) ensured a representative sample. These two variables were chosen to ensure adequate representation across linguistic and regional production contexts. The sample was drawn using the R function *samplei_strate()* with simple random sampling without the replacement method. Further, the stratum size was set proportional to the stratum population sizes, to ensure that each stratum was represented according to its share of population. Therefore, no probability proportional to size was used. Although the sampling was stratified, the analysis using unweighted and inverse probability-weighted samples (see Appendix K) produced similar results. A flow diagram outlining the sampling process can be found in Appendix I. The farmers received an invitation letter to participate in the study via postal service as well as a reminder letter 3 weeks after the initial distribution if they had not yet participated. They were free to choose whether they preferred a paper-and-pencil format or an online version of the survey, which we shared via a QR code and implemented in Tivian software (Tivian XI GmbH, 2021).

We controlled for the potential effects of the survey method on the

³ See <https://www.blw.admin.ch/blw/de/home/politik/datenmanagement/agate/agis.html>

Table 1
Overview of the tested hypotheses on farmers' intentions to adopt agroecological practices.

	Variable	Expected outcome	Literature
H1	Farm size		(Burton et al., 2003; Chatzimichael et al., 2014; Läßle, 2010; Läßle and Rensburg, 2011)
H2	Agroecological performance		(Breustedt et al., 2013; Siebert et al., 2010)
H3	Education		(Burton et al., 2003; Chatzimichael et al., 2014; Läßle and Kelley, 2015; Mzoughi, 2011; Sanchez-Mata et al., 2026)
H4	Gender (female)		(Heise and Theuvsen, 2016; Maas et al., 2021)
H5	Age (young)	Higher intention to adopt	(Granado-Díaz et al., 2022; Mack et al., 2020; Sanchez-Mata et al., 2026)
H6	Farm succession		(Daniele, 2024)
H7	Environmental and moral concerns (more positive)		(Breustedt et al., 2013; Burton et al., 2003; Läßle, 2010; Niens and Marggraf, 2010; Uthes and Matzdorf, 2013)
H8	Risk tolerance (higher)		(Kallas et al., 2010; Läßle and Kelley, 2013; Läßle and Rensburg, 2011; Trujillo-Barrera et al., 2016)
H9	Resistance to change (higher)	Lower intention to adopt	(Hermann et al., 2016; Rodriguez et al., 2009)
H10	Injunctive norms (stronger)	Higher intention to adopt	(Borges et al., 2014; Home et al., 2019; Läßle and Kelley, 2013; Lienhoop and Brouwer, 2015; Schreiner and Hess, 2017; Sereke et al., 2016; Siebert et al., 2010; Van Soest et al., 2015)
H11	Descriptive norms (stronger)		(Läßle and Kelley, 2015; Sok et al., 2016)
H12	Signaling motives (stronger)		(Heise and Theuvsen, 2016; Niens and Marggraf, 2010)
H13	Perceived financial risk (higher)	Lower intention to adopt	(Kallas et al., 2010; Niens and Marggraf, 2010; Trujillo-Barrera et al., 2016)
H14	Perceived control (higher)	Higher intention to adopt	(Mante and Gerowitz, 2009; Ridwansyah et al., 2024; Sapbamrer and Thammachai, 2021; Schukat et al., 2020; Xiang and Gao, 2023; Zhang et al., 2024)
H15	Perceived support (higher)		(Ridwansyah et al., 2024; Sapbamrer and Thammachai, 2021; Xiang and Gao, 2023; Zhang et al., 2024)
H16	Perceived resources (higher)	Higher intention to adopt	(Valdivia et al., 2012)
H17	Perceived knowledge (higher)		(Barnes et al., 2022; Dessart et al., 2019; Garforth et al., 2004; Power et al., 2013)
H18	Perceived cost (higher)	Lower intention to adopt	(Serebrennikov et al., 2020; Trujillo-Barrera et al., 2016)

Note: We did not formulate hypotheses for some of the variables (children, isolation, organic, farm type, temperature and precipitation), as they purely served as control variables.

Table 2
Comparison of key characteristics of the farm sample (n = 495) and the contacted farm population (n = 2001).^a

Characteristics	Description	Farm sample (only respondents) n = 495	Contacted farms n = 2001	p-value ^a
Farm size	Total agricultural land in hectares (mean)	19.2	19.2	0.6
Language: French	Percentage of farmers that chose French as corresponding language	17.2	13.8	–
Language: German	Percentage of farmers that chose German as corresponding language	82.8	86.2	–
Total livestock units	Measured in standard cattle units (SCU) (mean)	21.7	22.7	0.6
Workload ^c	Measured in standard working units (mean)	1.4	1.4	0.9
Organic	Percentage of organic farms	0.2	0.2	0.5
Mountain zone 1 ^b	Percentage of farms located in the mountain zone 1	0.3	0.2	–
Mountain zone 2 ^b	Percentage of farms located in the mountain zone 2	0.4	0.4	–
Mountain zone 3 ^b	Percentage of farms located in the mountain zone 3	0.1	0.2	–
Mountain zone 4 ^b	Percentage of farms located in the mountain zone 4	0.2	0.2	–

^a Pr(|Z| > |z|): * = 0.05; ** = 0.01; *** = 0.001.

^b The division of the mountain region follows the Swiss Agricultural Zones Ordinance (SR 912.1). which considers, in descending importance, the climatic conditions (especially vegetation period duration), accessibility (distance to the nearest village or center), and surface features (proportion of slopes and steep terrain).

^c One standard working unit equals 280 working days (Hoop and Schmid, 2015).

^{*} The contacted farm population (n = 2001) represents a representative sample of the total farm population of Switzerland. This allowed for a comparison between the survey respondents and the contacted farm population using the Wilcoxon rank sum test to assess the representativeness of the sample of respondents (n = 495).

results of our analysis by conducting robustness checks and ensuring that the mode of participation did not introduce any systematic bias. We found that the only differences between the participants was age, with online participants being younger on average and dairy farms being more likely to respond on paper (see Appendix H). Furthermore, to account for the participation mode in the analysis, we included it as a control variable in the regression models. The results were largely unchanged compared to models without this control (see Appendix L). Although a small number of coefficients exhibited marginal shifts in statistical significance, these changes did not affect the substantive interpretation of the findings.

Farmers were free to opt out of the survey at any time. They were also fully informed about data use and storage and had to agree to participate by giving their consent. We also asked farmers for their permission to

link their survey data with their AGIS data. The study received ethical approval from the Agroscope ethical committee (approval number: EK-AGS-2024-N02). The survey was first pre-tested with five grassland farmers to test the survey length and to ensure that the questions were understandable and unambiguous. Farmers who participated in the pre-test were not part of the final sample.

In total, we received 495 responses—out of the 2001 farms we contacted (response rate of 24.8%), with most participants (72.5%) choosing to respond using the paper-and-pencil format. We combined this survey data with AGIS data from 2024 on farm characteristics, such as farm size, livestock units, farm type (i.e., organic and non-organic), workload, and agricultural zones. We tested for significant differences between the sample and the population using Wilcoxon rank-sum tests and found the sample to be representative (Table 2; further details can be found in Appendix J). Regarding farm characteristics, although there was a slight overrepresentation of the French-speaking participants and farms located in the lowest mountain zone (i.e., mountain zone 1), we observed no significant difference between the sample of respondents ($n = 495$) and the contacted population ($n = 2001$). The survey data that support the findings of this study will be made available on Zenodo.

3.2. Survey design

In line with our conceptual model, the survey consisted of three main parts: (a) compilation of farm and farmer characteristics; (b) assessment of the agroecological performance for diversity, synergy, efficiency, and recycling, and the intention to increase the adoption of practices within the four elements; and (c) correlation of behavioral factors and related constructs. Cognitive and social factors were also collected for each of the four elements. The sequential structure of the survey is illustrated in Fig. 2. For an overview, we provide a complete version of the survey translated into English in the supplementary materials.

3.3. Variables of interest

The main variable assessed in the survey and used as the dependent variable in the analysis was the farmer's intention to adopt

agroecological practices across the four elements (i.e., diversity, synergy, efficiency, and recycling) (Table 3). We assessed the farmers' intentions using a 7-point Likert scale ranging from -3 (indicating a strong decrease) to $+3$ (indicating a strong increase) (see Table 3). To ensure a consistent understanding of the underlying agroecological practices, we provided the farmers with examples of practices for each element. These practices and their descriptions were validated by experts specializing in grassland agroecology. Therefore, the dependent variable reflects the farmers' intentions regarding an increase or decrease in farm diversification, synergies, the purchase of inputs and the generation of renewable energy. The survey question therefore included a definition of each agroecological element, followed by example practices related to the element rather. This approach was chosen to ensure that respondents shared a common understanding of the concept of agroecological being assessed, while avoiding restricting the interpretation of the concept to a fixed or exhaustive list of practices.

Tables 3 and 4 provide an overview of the other assessed variables (used as independent variables in the analysis). The variable “current agroecological performance” was calculated for each element using the Tool for Agroecology Performance Evaluation (TAPE) methodology developed by the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) of the United Nations (Mottet et al., 2020). We built on a version of the TAPE tool developed for farms in Switzerland by Gilgen et al. (2023). We then adapted this version for Swiss grassland farms. A more detailed overview of the items utilized can be found in Appendix A. For behavioral factors (i.e., dispositional, social, and cognitive factors), we used validated scales from the literature (e.g., New Ecological Paradigm from Dunlap et al., 2000; see Table 4). Historical levels of precipitation and temperature were obtained from the Swiss meteorological center and matched at the farm level (see Frei, 2014; Frei et al., 2006). This study was not pre-registered, and no pre-analysis plan was submitted. The selection of variables, econometric approach, and model specifications was based on a literature review and aligned with the objectives of the study.

Fig. 2. Survey design. This figure illustrates the different components of the survey, with arrows indicating sequential flow. Aligned with our conceptual framework, we classified our independent variables into four categories: (1) farm and farmer characteristics, (2) behavioral factors, (3) weather conditions, and (4) agroecological performance. The agroecological performance, farmers' intentions, and related behavioral factors were evaluated for each of the four agroecological elements, as indicated by the arrow on the right side of the figure.

Table 3
Description and summary statistics of the four dependent variables used in the analysis. The total sample size was 495.

Variable name	Original survey items/description	Unit (measurement scale)	Mean	SD
Intention to adopt diversity-related practices	<p>Question: Do you intend to change your on-farm diversification plans in future?</p> <p><i>We illustrated diversification plans for farmers as follows:</i> Various measures can be taken to increase farm diversification. For example: - Keep more different species or breeds of animals on the farm - Use more extensive meadows and pastures instead of intensive meadows and pastures - Keep pro specie rara rare breeds - Introduce new farm-related activities, for example, farm shop, ecotourism, 'sleeping in straw,' advisory services, teaching in a technical college, contract work</p>	Likert scale from <i>reduce considerably</i> (−3) to <i>increase considerably</i> (+3)	0.09	1.1
Intention to adopt synergy-related practices	<p>Question: Do you intend to limit or expand synergies between areas of your farm in future?</p> <p><i>We illustrated synergy plans for farmers as follows:</i> Synergies between different areas of the farm can be exploited. For example: - Use trees or hedges to provide shade for animals and protect against soil erosion - Promote connections between ecological focus areas - Exploit synergies between the home farm and the alpine farm/pastures. Use forage resources from alpine pastures in the summer - Feed on-farm milk to youngstock</p>	Likert scale from <i>limit synergies considerably</i> (−3) to <i>expand synergies considerably</i> (+3)	0.2	0.9
Intention to adopt efficiency-related practices	<p>Question: Do you intend to change the way you reuse resources on your farms in the future?</p> <p><i>We illustrated efficiency plans for farmers as follows:</i> You can take various measures to reduce the purchase of inputs (e. g., medicines,</p>	Likert scale from <i>reduce considerably</i> (−3) to <i>increase considerably</i> (+3)	−0.2	0.9

Table 3 (continued)

Variable name	Original survey items/description	Unit (measurement scale)	Mean	SD
Intention to adopt recycling-related practices	<p>feedstuff, fertilizers, machinery, youngstock, etc.), for example: - Raise youngstock and breeding stock on the farm instead of buying matured stock - Feed more forage to ruminants instead of concentrated feed - Buy in less forage - Buy in less mineral fertilizer - Treat livestock with prophylactics to prevent diseases</p> <p>Question: Do you intend to change the way you reuse resources on your farm in future?</p> <p><i>We illustrated recycling plans for farmers as follows:</i> Various measures can be taken to generate renewable energy. For example: - Use more residues and byproducts (e.g., fertilizer from recycled materials) - Install a heat pump or solar plant - Install equipment (e. g., tank) for harvesting rainwater</p>	Likert scale from <i>reduce considerably</i> (−3) to <i>increase considerably</i> (+3)	0.6	0.9

3.4. Data analysis

We do not have a causal identification strategy for a large number of potential drivers of adoption in a complex and interrelated system. Therefore, we carefully interpret our results as correlations (and not causal effects) and offer the results from a range of robustness tests. In our main analysis, and due to the ordinal nature of our dependent variables, we conducted separate ordinal regression analyses for each of the four dependent variables. This allowed us to assess factors that were statistically significantly related to the intention to adopt practices for each agroecological element, controlling for a wide range of other relevant variables:

$$(3) \text{Adoption}_{i,e} = \beta_{10} + \beta_1 \text{farm and farmer characteristics}_i + \beta_2 \text{weather conditions}_i + \beta_3 \text{dispositional factors}_i + \beta_4 \text{cognitive factors}_{i,e} + \beta_5 \text{social factors}_{i,e} + \beta_6 \text{agroecological performance}_{i,e} + \epsilon_{i,e}$$

where Y is the adoption intention ($\text{Adoption}_{i,e}$) for farmer i and agroecology element $e \in \{\text{diversity, synergies, efficiency, recycling}\}$. $\text{Adoption}_{i,e}$ denotes an ordinal dependent variable taking values from −3 to +3 (higher values indicate higher adoption intention) and β_0 the intercept. In line with our conceptual model, we considered farm and farmers' characteristics, dispositional factors, social factors, cognitive factors, weather conditions, and agroecological performance as explanatory variables. β_1 to β_6 are their respective regression coefficients, and $\epsilon_{i,e}$ is

Table 4
Description and summary statistics of the independent variables used in the analysis. The total sample size was 495..

Variable name	Original survey items /description	Unit (measurement scale)	Mean	SD
Organic farming		Share in %	23.0	
Farm size		ha	19.2	13.5
Current agroecological performance: diversity (Adapted from: FAO, 2019 ; Gilgen et al., 2023)	Four questions allowed us to evaluate the performance score of a farm in a specific domain. Farmers could score up to 12 points per element, which were summed up and transformed into a percentage point. (Detailed item formulations used to measure performance can be found in Appendix A.)	% Points	44.8	12.7
Current agroecological performance: synergies (Adapted from: FAO, 2019 ; Gilgen et al., 2023)	Four questions allowed us to evaluate the performance score of a farm in a specific domain. Farmers could score up to 12 points per element, which were summed up and transformed into a percentage point. (Detailed item formulations used to measure performance can be found in Appendix A.)	% Points	68.5	10.4
Current agroecological performance: efficiency (Adapted from: FAO, 2019 ; Gilgen et al., 2023)	Four questions allowed us to evaluate the performance score of a farm in a specific domain. Farmers could score up to 12 points per element, which were summed up and transformed into a percentage point. (Detailed item formulations used to measure performance can be found in Appendix A.)	% Points	67.4	10.4
Current agroecological performance: recycling (Adapted from: FAO, 2019 ; Gilgen et al., 2023)	Four questions allowed us to evaluate the performance score of a farm in a specific domain. Farmers could score up to 12 points per element, which were summed up and transformed into a percentage point. (Detailed item formulations used to measure performance can be found in Appendix A.)	% Points	48.9	9.7
Farm Type				
1 = Dairy (dummy)		Share in %	40.6	
2 = Suckler cows		Share in %	14.6	
3 = Horses/sheep/goats/other cattle		Share in %	34.6	
4 = Others		Share in %	10.3	
Education				
1 = without high school diploma		Share in %	80.2	

Table 4 (continued)

Variable name	Original survey items /description	Unit (measurement scale)	Mean	SD
2 = with high school diploma		Share in %		16.6
Gender	(1 = Female; 0 = Male)	Share in % (female)	13.6	
Age		Years (continuous)	48	11.6
Kids		Number of kids living on the farm	1.1	1.4
Farm income	Proportion of the income from farm activities	Share in %	62	32.7
Isolation	1 = next farm is more than 500 m away; 0 = next farm is less than 500 m away)	Share in % (next farm is more than 500 m away)		24.7
Farm succession in next 5 years	1 = Farm stays in current possession (dummy)	Share in %		77.3
2 = Farm will be managed by someone else		Share in %		8.5
3 = Farm will be sold		Share in %		3.2
4 = Not clear yet		Share in %		10.3
Dispositional factors				
Environmental and moral concerns (Validated scale from Dunlap et al., 2000)	People have the right to change their natural environment to suit their needs.	Measured on a five-point Likert scale from 1 ("do not agree at all") to 5 ("fully correct")	2.51	0.5
Risk tolerance (Adapted from: Möhrling and Finger, 2022)	Marketing and selling your own products.	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 ("very unwilling to take risks") to 7 ("very willing to take risks")	4.3	1.2
Resistance to change (Validated scale from Oregon, 2003)	I'd rather be bored than surprised.	Measured on a six-point Likert scale from 1 ("strongly disagree") to 6 ("strongly agree")	3.0	0.7
Social factors ^d	Most agricultural consultants/farmers in my region believe that it is important to diversify my farm.	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 ("not correct at all") to 7 ("fully correct")		
Injunctive norms: Consultant and peers	(Adapted from: Le Coent et al., 2021 based on Ajzen, 1991)	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 ("not correct at all") to 7 ("fully correct")	4.2	1.18
Injunctive norms: Scientists, environmentalist, society	Swiss society believe that it is important to diversify my farm. (Adapted from: Le Coent et al., 2021 based on Ajzen, 1991)	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 ("not correct at all") to 7 ("fully correct")	5.2	1.4
Descriptive norms	Most farmers in my region have already diversified. (Adapted from: Le Coent et al., 2021)	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 ("not correct at all") to 7 ("fully correct")	4	1.2
Signaling motives	Measures aimed at diversifying production improve the image of my farm.	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 ("not correct at all") to 7 ("fully correct")	4.8	1.4
Cognitive Factors ^a				
Perceived risk	Taking new measures aimed at diversifying production on my farm is financially risky.	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 ("not correct at all") to 7 ("fully correct")	3.7	1.1

(continued on next page)

Table 4 (continued)

Variable name	Original survey items /description	Unit (measurement scale)	Mean	SD
Perceived control	<i>It is entirely my responsibility to introduce measures to diversify my farm.</i> (Adapted from: Borges et al., 2014)	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 (“not correct at all”) to 7 (“fully correct”)	5.4	1.3
Perceived support	<i>I have sufficient support from the retail industry/agricultural sector to take measures to diversify production.</i>	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 (“not correct at all”) to 7 (“fully correct”)	3.5	1.4
Perceived resources	<i>I have sufficient resources (infrastructure and technical resources) to take measures to diversify production.</i> (Adapted from: Borges et al., 2014)	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 (“not correct at all”) to 7 (“fully correct”)	4.4	1.4
Perceived knowledge	<i>I have sufficient knowledge to take measures to diversify production.</i> (Adapted from: Borges et al., 2014)	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 (“not correct at all”) to 7 (“fully correct”)	5.31	1.18
Perceived costs	<i>I see more economic costs than benefits in taking measures to diversify my farm.</i>	Measured on a seven-point Likert scale from 1 (“not correct at all”) to 7 (“fully correct”)	4.25	1.36
<i>Weather conditions</i>				
Temperature	Average yearly mean temperatures on the farm over the last 30 years obtained and matched at farm level	°C	7.4	1.3
Precipitation	Average yearly amount of on the farm over the last 30 years obtained and matched at farm level	(1/m ²)	1390.1	290.6

^a All examples of the item formulation provided in Table 4 are the original ones we used to evaluate the element of diversity. The original items used for measuring synergy, efficiency, and recycling differ only slightly from those used for diversity and can be found in the supplementary materials.

the respective error term. We used the (clm) function in R⁴ to estimate the function. We used ordinal regression in the main model, since the groups were ordered on a numerical scale from -3 to +3 with the same distance between the groups. The models used complete-case estimation. The models used complete-case estimation. After the pre-test of the questionnaire, a deliberate “I don’t know” option was added to the social factors, as pre-tested farmers had indicated that they were unable to form a meaningful opinion. This approach aligns with previous research indicating that adding such an option reduces satisficing and captures genuinely unformed or absent attitudes (Bishop et al., 1986; Krosnick, 1991). “I don’t know” responses were treated as missing values (see Appendix M for the missingness table). In addition, we conducted Little’s MCAR test to analyze the nature of the missingness. To analyze the missing data, we applied multivariate imputation using the function mice in R (with fully conditional specification). We also checked for robustness using ordinal regression.

⁴ The dataset was analyzed using R version 4.2.1 (R Core Team: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing, R Foundation for Statistical Computing, 2022).

3.5. Robustness check

First, we checked whether accounting for potential correlations of dependent variables (diversity, synergies, efficiency, recycling) with each other (i.e., a farmer’s intention to adopt one practice could influence their intention to adopt another) affects results, using seemingly unrelated regression (SUR). SUR allows for the simultaneous estimation of multiple regression equations, under the assumption that the errors across equations are correlated (Elhorst, 2003). The generalized least squares technique, accounting for the variance-covariance matrix of the error terms, was used to estimate the SUR. As noted by Guliyev (2024), the components of the variance matrix are unknown, which can be addressed by approximating the matrix using residuals from a separate OLS estimation, forming the basis for the generalized least squares estimation in the model (Zellner, 1962). Second, we conducted a hierarchical ordinal regression to assess the contribution of the different predictor sets. Third, a linear regression was performed to verify the robustness of the results. Fourth, to differentiate between drivers for the intention to increase or reduce agroecology, we built three groups based on the score: “reduce” (-3 to -1), “no change” (0), and “increase” (1 to 3). We then analyzed this new dependent variable using multinomial logistic regression, as the multinomial specification does not rely on proportional odds assumptions:

$$(4) \log \left(\frac{P(Y_i = k|X_i)}{P(Y_i = K|X_i)} \right) = \beta_{10k} + \beta_{1k} \text{farm and farmer characteristics}_i + \beta_{2k} \text{weather conditions}_i + \beta_{3k} \text{dispositional factors}_i + \beta_{4k} \text{cognitive factors}_{i,e} + \beta_{5k} \text{social factors}_{i,e} + \beta_{6k} \text{Agroecological performance}_{i,e} + \epsilon_i$$

where Y is the categorical dependent outcome variable for farmer i , k represents the three outcome categories of “reduce,” “no change,” and “increase,” and K is the reference category (in our case, the “no change”). e represents the agroecology elements {diversity, synergies, efficiency, recycling}, β indicates the respective coefficients to be estimated, and ϵ_i is the error term. This model computes the log-odds for each category and compares them to the base category, where β_{ik} denotes the effect of predictors on the log-odds of membership from the categories “increase” and “decrease” relative to the reference category “no change”. We used the “nnet” package in R (Venables and Ripley, 2002) for estimations.

Fifth, we checked for omitted variable bias to evaluate the degree of unobservable to observable necessary to render the results. Therefore, we evaluated the degree of proportional selection required to reduce the treatment effect to zero under a maximum R2 set, following Oster’s (2019) recommendation (1.3 times the R2 of the full model). Using the R package “robomit,” we computed both the bias-adjusted coefficient under the assumption for equal selection of observable and unobservable and the corresponding δ values. We conducted a separate LASSO regression for the four dependent variables using a minimal lambda obtained through cross-validation. This allows for optimal predictive performance by minimizing the cross-validated mean squared error while retraining theoretically relevant predictors. The model was estimated using the glmnet package in R, with the regularization parameter fixed at 1. To identify the optimal level of regularization, cv.glmnet in R was applied. The minimum lambda value was selected, as it minimized the cross-validated mean squared error. This allowed for optimal predictive performance while keeping relevant predictors. We then extracted the coefficient at the selected lambda value, and reduced the coefficient for irrelevant predictors to zero for exclusion from the model.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive results: Adoption intention of agroecological practices

In the context of this study, farmers' intention to adopt agroecology is reflected through their intention to increase or decrease farm diversity, synergies, input purchase, and renewable energy generation. We begin by comparing the farmers' intentions to adopt agroecology across the four elements using an eANOVA test (ezANOVA function in R). The intentions differed significantly across the different elements ($F(3, 1371) = 70.70, p < .001$), with the highest intention observed for practices related to recycling. These practices focused on reducing losses of nutrients, water, and biomass (mean $[M] = 0.56$, standard deviation $[SD] = 0.94$). This was followed by the element of synergies, which refers to beneficial interactions among system components ($M = 0.24, SD = 0.93$). The element of diversity, which involves having a wide variety of species, genetic resources, and agroecological interactions within the farming system, ranked next ($M = 0.09, SD = 1.07$). Notably, the intention to adopt efficiency-related practices was negative ($M = -0.21, SD = 0.91$).

Overall, for all elements, the largest share of farmers did not wish to change their status quo (see Fig. 3). A correlation analysis between the different elements showed that the intentions were significantly correlated, with Pearson correlation coefficients ranging from 0.44 to 0.12, all statistically significant at $p < .001$ (Appendix B).

4.2. Regression analysis: Drivers of adoption

To examine the drivers of the intention to enhance diversity, synergies, efficiency, and recycling, we conducted a regression analysis (Fig. 4; see Appendix C for detailed regression results). We explored the factors related to adoption, which were divided into categories based on the farm and farmers' characteristics, behavioral factors, and natural conditions. This section is structured accordingly. All variables were checked for multicollinearity, and none were found. All variance inflation factors (VIF) were under the 2.5 threshold, and no pairwise correlation coefficient exceeded 0.7 (see Appendix O for correlation heatmaps). We interpret our results as correlations and not as causal relations.

Regarding farm and farmers' characteristics, the results indicated that female farmers tended to show a higher likelihood of increasing diversity ($p = .004$). Younger farmers were more likely to increase diversity ($p = .001$), synergy ($p = .001$) and recycling ($p = .027$). Further, farms with a greater off-farm income were more likely to adopt efficiency ($p = .004$) related practices. Farms whose neighbors were located more than 500 m away were more likely to adopt synergies ($p = .041$) and efficiency related practices ($p = .043$). An unclear farm

succession decreased farmers' intention to adopt synergies related practices ($p = .034$).

Regarding behavioral factors, farmers with higher risk tolerance were more likely to adopt diversity-enhancing practices ($p < .001$). Further, the more important injunctive norms were to the farmers, reflecting the approval of peers and advisors, the more likely they were to adopt diversity-related practices ($p < .001$). Higher injunctive norms were associated with a decrease in efficiency-related practices ($p = .01$). We further found that the more developed the farmers' descriptive norms (i.e., representing the observed behavior of peers), the less likely they were to adopt diversity-promoting practices ($p = .01$). The more important it was for the farmers to project a certain image (i.e., signaling motives), the more likely they were to adopt synergy-related ($p < .001$) and recycling-related ($p < .001$) practices. The more support the farmers had, the greater their likelihood of adopting synergies ($p = 0.04$) and efficiency-related ($p = .01$) practices. However, the higher the farmers' perceived costs, the less likely they were to adopt and recycling-enhancing ($p = .003$) practices. Fig. 3 shows that although certain results were similar, there were differences in the drivers of the elements.

4.3. Robustness checks

We conducted several robustness checks. First, we used seemingly unrelated regression (SUR) and found that the model (see Appendix G) demonstrated a McElroy R^2 of 0.29 and a determinant of the residual covariance matrix (detRCov) of 0.13. Using the Breusch-Pagan test for residual correlation in SUR, we found that there was no significant residual correlation ($\chi^2(6) = 7.54, p = 0.27$). Furthermore, there were no substantial interdependencies among all the equations, and unobserved factors likely did not simultaneously influence all the dependent variables. This means that in our study, using the SUR to estimate every equation separately did not offer a significant advantage. The assumption of correlated error terms, which justified the central gain of using SUR, was not supported.

Second, we conducted an ordinal hierarchical regression analysis to evaluate the stability of the relationships identified in our initial model while accounting for the ordinal nature of the dependent variable (see Appendix E). Third, the results of the linear hierarchical regression (detailed in Appendix D) revealed that the coefficients for the independent variables remained mainly consistent with the findings of the ordinal regression. However, several variables changed in significance. For the element of synergies, isolation, unclear succession, and perceived support became significant/insignificant. For the element of efficiency, isolation and farm type showed changes in significance, while for the element of recycling, age became significant/non-significant. Furthermore, the results of the ordinal and linear hierarchical models showed that all key predictors remained significant across each

Fig. 3. Intention distribution: represents for each element of agroecology analyzed the percentage of farms that selected a particular intention level for each element of agroecology analyzed in this study, with -3 representing a strong intention to reduce and +3 representing a strong intention to increase the presence of the agroecological element on the farm (sample size (n): diversity = 487; synergies = 459; efficiency = 470; recycling = 472).

Fig. 4. Results of the regression analysis with dependent variables of diversity ($n = 225$), synergies ($n = 224$), efficiency ($n = 224$), and recycling ($n = 225$). Note: This plot visualizes the direction and significance of the regression coefficients across multiple dependent variables. The x-axis represents the farmers' intentions to adopt agroecological practices related to the elements of diversity, synergies, efficiency, and recycling. Each tile's color indicates the direction of the estimated coefficients (green = positive, blue = negative), and its transparency reflects its statistical significance. The full regression results (odds ratio and standard errors) can be found in Appendix E 1–4. For all models, the cumulative likelihood model (clm) was compared to an intercept-only model to determine the likelihood-ratio test (Christensen, 2019). The predictors jointly explained: -Regression statistics for adopting diversity: LR X^2 ($df = 30$) = 93.4, $p < .001$; -Regression results for adopting synergies: LR X^2 ($df = 30$) = 70, $p < .001$; -Regression results for adopting efficiency: LR X^2 ($df = 30$) = 48.3, $p = .01$; -Regression results for adopting recycling: LR X^2 ($df = 30$) = 63, $p < .001$. (1) Reference farm type: dairy farms; (2) gender (1 = female; 0 = male); (3) isolation (1 = neighbor is more than 500 m away; 0 = neighbor is less than 500 m); and (4) succession (reference: Farm stays in current possession)

regression step, with consistent directions and similar effect sizes, indicating robust associations.

Fourth, we examined the potential drivers that could increase or decrease practices related to the four key elements. To this end, we used a multinomial regression analysis (see Appendix F). The multinomial regression exhibited slightly better AIC and BIC compared with the corresponding ordered regression (see Appendix F). The results were in line with the linear regression results. The multinomial regression revealed that some drivers that were non-significant in the linear regression were associated with either a significant decrease or increase in practices, but not both. For example, organic farms were less likely to reduce diversity, but they were also less likely to increase practices

related to synergy and efficiency. When a family member was expected to take over the farm within the next five years, current farm managers were more likely to reduce diversity. They were also less likely to reduce synergies and more likely to increase efficiency-related practices. Additionally, farmers without neighbors within 500 m were more likely to reduce synergies and recycling practice adoption and showed no intention of increasing them. Fifth, across all four regressions, the Oster bound results (both δ and the bias-adjusted coefficients) remained large ($\delta > 1$), indicating that a substantially stronger selection on unobservable than on observables would be required to overturn the main findings.

We further applied a robustness check using Lasso regression. We

found that many key variables identified in the main regression were mostly also selected by the lasso model, supporting the robustness of the original findings (see Appendix P). Interestingly, some variables that were statistically significant in the main models were not retained by the lasso model. This pattern was particularly evident for synergies and efficiency, where fewer predictors were selected compared to diversity and recycling, where additional predictors were identified.

5. Discussion

Agroecology could offer a promising pathway for the sustainable transformation of agriculture because of its holistic and transdisciplinary approach. Yet, despite its growing relevance in policy and scientific debates, there is still limited research on the adoption of agroecological practices, and the key factors needed to scale up agroecology in Europe. We analyzed farmers' intention to increase or decrease farm diversity, synergies, input purchase, and renewable energy generation, taking a holistic view across different elements of agroecology.

Our results reveal that across all four agroecological elements (diversity, synergies, efficiency, and recycling), the largest proportion of farmers in our sample (47–70%, depending on the element) did not intend to change their agroecological performance (see Fig. 2). Notably, for the element of recycling, a substantial share of 48% (which was also the highest) of the farms expressed an intention to adopt further agroecological practices. By contrast, for diversity and synergies, the intention to increase these elements was lower but still exceeded 27% of farms. Efficiency related practices stood out as an exception, with around 21% of farms indicating a desire to reduce agroecological practices.

Although a large share of farmers in our sample did not intend to adopt further practices across most elements, the observed variation between the elements suggests that some degree of change was still taking place and reflects the distinct characteristics of the agroecological elements. This variability could be attributed to the specific characteristics of each agroecological element, as each reflects different aspects, although they are interconnected. This could also be explained by differing perceptions of complexity, risk, or compatibility with existing systems, as highlighted by Wezel et al. (2020). Among the elements assessed, recycling-related practices showed the highest intention to increase. This may be attributed to the potential economic and environmental benefits of recycling practices (e.g., biogas or solar energy production). These results confirm the findings of a German study that found dairy and livestock farms to be among the early adopters of solar panels (Feuerbacher et al., 2021). The intention to increase synergy- and diversity- related practices on grassland farms could be driven by resilience targets. This is supported by studies highlighting the feasibility and benefits of improved forage production, biodiversity conservation, and ecosystem resilience through ecological integration (Accatino et al., 2019; Bengtsson et al., 2019; Peili et al., 2020). By contrast, the low intention to increase low-input practices (efficiency) may be associated with higher risks and uncertainty, as the transition to such practices often requires initial investments and changes in management practices, such as on-farm rearing. Additionally, the complexity of implementing such changes could discourage farmers from adopting efficiency-related practices.

Although previous studies have suggested that larger farms may be better positioned to implement agroecological practices due to economies of scale (Chatzimichael et al., 2014; Niens and Marggraf, 2010), our findings do not reflect this. This outcome contradicts our hypothesis and indicates that farm size alone may not be sufficient to drive the adoption intention of practices relates to the element of agroecological practices (H1). This finding is consistent with the results of a recent quantitative meta-analysis of European studies on agroecology (Sanchez-Mata et al., 2026). This analysis suggests that farm size exerts a small and inconsistent effect and is not a statistically significant

determinant of adoption. Furthermore, farmers with higher agroecological performance did not show greater adoption intentions across all elements, although this was expected (H2). Considering farmers' characteristics, although education was expected to increase adoption intention (H3), our findings did not confirm this. This may reflect threshold effects, in which additional education does not necessarily translate into greater adoption intention (Chatzimichael et al., 2014; Läßle and Kelley, 2015).

In line with our expectations (H4, H5), we find that farmers' gender and age were related to adoption intention, although their significance varied depending on the specific element. For the element of diversity, female farmers showed higher adoption intentions. These results are in line with findings by Gomori-Ruben and Reid (2023), who observed that female-led agroecological initiatives in the U.S. are often linked to diversification. Diversification can also offer additional income opportunities, which may further motivate women to engage in such practices (Fremstad and Paul, 2020). Regarding the elements of diversity and synergies, younger farmers expressed higher adoption intentions. These results suggest that they are more open to change, more future-oriented, or more familiar with agroecological concepts. By contrast, older farmers may exhibit a preference for established routines (Rivaroli et al., 2017; Ullah and Shivakoti, 2014). This pattern is consistent with a recent review article, which identifies age as a barrier to unlocking agroecology in the European region (Sanchez-Mata et al., 2026). Despite the incorporation of off-farm income as a control variable, its substantial impact indicates that it exerts a specific influence on adoption intention, particularly in regard to efficiency-related practices. This is presumably attributable to the provision of supplementary financial flexibility to farmers, enabling the investment in productivity-enhancing measures (Fronzel et al., 2012; Läßle, 2010). As posited by Sanchez-Mata et al. (2026), the phenomenon of diver effect appears to be associated with a decline in the reliance on farm income. This, in turn, has been demonstrated to reduce the risk of short-term losses and to facilitate the adoption of agroecological practices by farmers (Lastra-Bravo et al., 2015). Furthermore, the absence of clear plans for farm succession (H6) decreased the adoption intention of synergies-related practices. This suggests that farms facing uncertainty are less likely to make changes regarding the adoption of practices to enhance the synergies performance of their farms.

We also find that behavioral factors were key to the adoption of practices associated to the element of agroecology. All behavioral factors were significantly related to the adoption of all elements, although these relationships are based on stated intentions and effective sample (although representative of the total population) varies across specification. Regarding dispositional factors, only farmers' risk tolerance was a driver of adoption (rejecting H7 and H9 and supporting H8). For the element of diversity, farmers' risk tolerance was positively associated with higher intentions. This finding aligns with our expectations (H8). However, this relationship is not consistent across all four elements of agroecology, suggesting that the influence of risk attitudes may vary depending on the practice. As expected, (H10–H13), social factors (e.g., signaling motives, descriptive norms, and injunctive norms) were significant predictors across all elements. For the element of diversity, injunctive norms from consultants and peers increased adoption intention in our sample, as expected. However, descriptive norms seemed to decrease farm diversity. This is contrary to our hypothesis suggesting that descriptive norms should increase adoption intention (H11). These results indicate that farmers' perceptions of what is socially acceptable increase their adoption intention, while the behavior commonly performed by others decreases it. Prokopy et al. (2008) suggested that farmers are more likely to adopt practices viewed as socially acceptable in their community, as injunctive norms create social pressure to conform. Conversely, if widely adopted practices are seen as ineffective, farmers may be deterred from adopting them, as descriptive norms can misalign with social endorsement (Rimal and Lapinski, 2015).

Regarding the element of efficiency, injunctive norms from society,

environmentalists, and scientists were associated with a decrease in adoption intention. Although Sereke et al. (2016) observed the opposite within agroforestry practices in Switzerland, external promotion can conflict with local customs or beliefs, and farmers may resist adopting these practices, perceiving them as imposed rather than beneficial for them (Ogundari and Bolarinwa, 2018). In support of H12, across the elements of synergies and recycling, farmers' adoption was related to signaling norms (i.e., the image portrayed by their farm). This could be explained by the high visibility of some of these practices (i.e., hedges in fields or solar panels on roofs), which could encourage adoption by showcasing commitment to sustainable farming and enhancing credibility among peers and consumers (Dumbrell et al., 2016; Prokopy et al., 2008).

Regarding cognitive factors, we find that perceived support (supporting H15) and perceived cost (supporting H18) were the single relevant cognitive factors. For the elements of efficiency and synergies, farmers' perceived support was associated with a higher adoption intention. Similarly, a study in Italy found that adoption patterns were heavily influenced by the effectiveness of support services (Rosa et al., 2020). Supportive conditions have also been shown to play a key role in promoting organic farming adoption (Sapbamrer and Thammachai, 2021). Concerning the element of recycling, we observe that a high-cost perception tended to lower the adoption of recycling practices. Recycling practices often involve upfront and adjustment costs, which can deter adoption if farmers are unable to invest (Darnhofer, 2010; Feliciano, 2019). Recycling is the only element reflecting costs, and it is a more economic factor as a key determinant of adoption. Furthermore, perceived risk, control, resources, and knowledge are expected to impact farmers' adoption intention (H13, H14, H16, and H17); our results do not support these hypotheses. Similar findings have been reported, especially with resource-intensive practices (Zeweld et al., 2017) or among farmers whose informal knowledge and social learning outweigh self-perceived competence (Ha et al., 2023). Overall, these behavioral patterns are indicative of relationships within the studied sample rather than definitive evidence of causal or population wide effect.

Our results are stable over a range of robustness checks. The SUR showed no substantial interdependencies among any of the equations. The assumption of correlated error terms, which justified using the SUR model, was not supported. The results of the hierarchical model showed that all key predictors remained significant across each regression step, with consistent directions and similar effect sizes, indicating robust associations. The ordinal regression (detailed in Appendix E) revealed that the coefficients for the independent variables remained mainly consistent. By comparing the results of the ordinal regression with those from the hierarchical linear model, we ensured that our findings were consistent and robust to the choice of analytical approach. The results of the multinomial regression also suggest that the farm production system (i.e., being organic or not) plays a role in shaping adoption intention. Organic farmers appeared less likely to increase synergies and efficiency, possibly because these elements were already well-integrated within their system. There was even a tendency for organic farms to reduce recycling, which may reflect shifting priorities or trade-offs within organic practices. By contrast, diversity stood out as the one domain in which organic farmers still showed some adoption intention.

Isolation appeared to reduce farmers' intention to increase synergy and efficiency, which supports our main finding that signaling motives (i.e., farmers' desire to project a certain image) play a key role in increasing the agroecological performance. Given that isolation limits visibility to others, the incentive to adopt visible, image-enhancing practices, such as synergy and recycling, could be reduced. Moreover, when succession was expected within five years and within the family, the farmers tended to avoid diversification but focused more on maintaining synergies and improving efficiency. This could be because farmers prioritize maintaining the existing system and improving efficiency to strengthen the farm's resilience to prepare the farm for the next generation. This aligns with findings in European farming, where clarity

about future management has been shown to encourage more proactive, future-oriented decision-making (Daniele, 2024).

Overall, across these alternative model specifications, the core findings remained largely stable, affirming the robustness of our conclusions, despite minor shifts in the significance of some variables. Collectively, these checks strengthened confidence in the internal validity and reliability of our results. Furthermore, regarding the omitted variables, the Oster bound results indicate that although our results are not causal, the likelihood that omitted variables bias causes a problem is very low.

Nonetheless, some limitations of the study should be acknowledged. Self-reported intentions may be subject to social desirability bias and may not always translate into actual behavior—a known intention–behavior gap (Ajzen, 1991). This has important implications for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners. Researchers have suggested that predictors of the intention to adopt sustainable farming practices do not always predict the actual behavior (Byfuglien et al., 2025; Hasler et al., 2022; Kollmuss and Agyeman, 2002; Mills et al., 2020). Furthermore, social dynamics may shape intentions, but this does not necessarily lead to behavioral change (Milliet et al., 2024; Niles et al., 2016). While past behavior can predict both intentions and actual adoption (Niles et al., 2016), our results do not suggest that farmers with higher agroecological performance have a higher adoption intention. The gap between intention and action may be closed by facilitating the translation from intention to action by increasing the self-efficacy levels (Conner and Norman, 2022). In our case, increased perceived support suggests a higher intention to expand the elements synergy and efficiency. For these elements, interventions should further focus on addressing the step required to convert intention into behaviors. Second, we focused on mountainous grassland farms in Switzerland. This is a highly relevant context for agroecology, but future studies should expand the analysis toward other types of production systems and regions to compare observed patterns. Also, the sample excluded Italian-speaking participants and certain legal forms and farm types, which may restrict the generalization of the findings to the entire Swiss population (see Appendix I). Regarding the intention measurement, because the intention item included multiple example practices, we could not determine which specific practices the respondents intended to adopt. The intention item reflects the farmers' intentions regarding an increase or decrease in farm diversification, synergies, input purchases and renewable energy generation. Therefore, it was not possible to determine which specific practices the respondents intended to increase or decrease. Examples of practices and descriptions of elements were included to help respondents understand the scope of each element and to make the concept more concrete. As asking about individual practices would substantially increase the length of the survey, this approach reflects the trade-off between survey duration and question specificity. In line with our approach, recent research on survey design has addressed these trade-offs and suggested that more aggregated questions may be preferable when the overarching and more detailed definitions correspond well with each other (Slijper et al., 2025). The order of the agroecological elements and examples was not randomized either, which may have introduced anchoring effects. In addition, some elements (e.g., efficiency vs. recycling) have different numbers of practice examples. Our measurement strategy prioritizes alignment with the FAO TAPE tool's conceptualization of agroecological elements over the development of the intention scales. In addition, some elements (e.g., efficiency vs. recycling) have different numbers of practice examples. Our measurement strategy prioritizes alignment with the FAO TAPE tool's conceptualization of agroecological elements over the development of the intention scales.

Furthermore, in response to feedback from the pre-test of the questionnaire, participants were given the option to select "I don't know" when reporting behavioral intentions. In line with previous research, this avoids the inclusion of arbitrary answers and pressuring respondents to give opinions when they plead ignorance (Bishop et al.,

1986; Krosnick, 1991). We coded these responses as missing values (NA) rather than treating them as neutral, based on prior evidence that behavioral intention factors are less likely to reflect genuine uncertainty and more likely to signal a lack of thought about the behavior or an unwillingness to provide an opinion (Ajzen, 1991; Rosenstock, 1974). Treating “I don't know” as neutral would therefore risk misrepresenting the construct. Therefore, this approach generated substantially more missing values than for other constructs (see Appendix M for the missingness table). However, this approach resulted in a significant MCAR test (when looking only at variables with NA), and subsequent imputations produced divergent results (see Appendix M), highlighting that our handling of “I don't know” responses may have influenced the findings. However, the consistency in the direction and relative importance of key predictors across model specifications suggests that the underlying relationships remain robust among respondents who had formed opinions on these behaviors. For policymakers and researchers, these findings are therefore informative in identifying relevant levers of change.

Moreover, given the nature of our data, a hurdle model that separates the adoption/non-adoption decision from the decision to intensify adoption would theoretically be most appropriate for analyzing farmer decisions. However, such models only provide additional insights when sets of explanatory variables differ, requiring clear theoretical or empirical evidence on why to exclude/include variables in one equation and not the other. Since discussions with experts and the literature did not provide such indications, we chose a single-hurdle model for our analysis. In addition, the regression models showed low adjusted R² values, indicating that the predictors accounted for only a proportion of the variance in the outcomes. This score is not unexpected and reflects several structural features of the analysis. Further, R² tends to be smaller in studies with a larger number of predictors relative to sample size, in cross-sectional studies, and when using primary data (Reisinger, 1997). First, the model includes a large set of conceptual predictors that result in measurement compression and limit the amount of unique variance from single variables. Second, some of the behavioral factors naturally share variance, which reflects theoretical relatedness. Although it does not constitute problematic multicollinearity (see Appendix O), it reduces statistical power and can increase uncertainty around some estimates. Further, the relatively high number of predictors related to the total number of completed observations strains the degree of freedom, reducing the statistical power and further destabilizing the model estimate. Although dimension reduction could mitigate these effects, we intentionally retained the construct as a separate predictor, as the multicollinearity was not problematic. All VIF values under 2.5, which is under the cutoff recommendation of (Sheather, 2009) and the correlation coefficients do not exceed 0.7, as the aim of the study is to examine the variation across the different aspects of behavioral factors rather than collapse them into broader latent dimensions. Therefore, the low adjusted R² values should be interpreted as a reflection of the model structure and the characteristics of the assessed variable rather than as evidence that the underlying relationships are weak or unimportant (Ozili, 2022).

6. Conclusion

Agroecology is a holistic approach to sustainable agriculture that emphasizes the interaction of multiple elements of agroecology. However, the literature on the drivers of the uptake of practices that improve the agroecological performance of farms is limited, and existing studies do not consider the multifaceted, holistic nature of agroecology. We examined Swiss grassland farmers' intentions to adopt agroecological practices across four key elements of agroecology and analyzed their structural and behavioral drivers.

A comparison of farmers' intentions to adopt agroecology across these elements revealed the highest intention scores for recycling practices, followed by synergies, diversity, and efficiency. This

highlights that farmers do not adopt agroecology as a package but selectively engage with different elements, reflecting the complexity of adoption mechanisms within holistic farming systems. An agroecological transition might require changes not only by adopting single practices but a transformation of farm structures and their business model (Sanchez-Mata et al., 2026). We find that drivers of scaling agroecology differed across elements, but some patterns emerged. Social norms emerged as key drivers across elements, yet their influence varied. For instance, injunctive norms (what others think one should do) promoted the adoption of diversity- and efficiency-enhancing practices, while descriptive norms (what peers are doing) undermined such adoptions. Importantly, perceived cost–benefit ratios influenced recycling, but not the other elements.

These insights have significant implications for scaling agroecology. We find that scaling must be rooted in an understanding that “one-size-fits-all” policy approaches are unlikely to succeed. Instead, targeted strategies tailored to the (behavioral) drivers of each agroecological element are necessary. For example, we find that for diversity, reducing perceived risks through targeted support and fostering peer exchange could shift social norms. This implies that policy interventions aiming to scale up agroecology could strategically incorporate social factor-based approaches (i.e., social norms nudges or signaling factors) to increase the agroecological performance of farms related to specific elements. Further, for efficiency, an increase in perceived support (i.e., from retail or the agricultural sector) could positively influence farmers' adoption intentions. For recycling, financial incentives are key, and the visibility of the element allows for leveraging social signaling. Importantly, policies should be context-sensitive, reflecting the specific agroecological elements, cultural, and socio-economic conditions of farmers. It is important to note that our findings are based on stated intentions and a reduced analytical sample; consequently, they should not be interpreted as fully representative of the broader farming population, but rather as indicative of patterns among farmers who have actively engaged with these concepts.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andreia Arbenz: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Gabriele Mack:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Jeanine Ammann:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Niklas Möhring:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Ethics statement

All the participants provided written informed consent before starting the survey. Their involvement was voluntary, and they were free to exit the study at any time if they wished to do so. Ethical guidelines were followed, and the ethics committee of Agroscope reviewed and approved the study (ethical approval number: EK-AGS-2024-N02).

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2026.109103>.

Data availability

The survey data, the questionnaires (including all language versions and English translation) and the codebook will be made available on Zenodo.

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